

AUTOMATED CAR WITH RAIN SENSOR

¹Sayantana Maitra, ¹Md Avaish Siddiqui, ¹Rahul Raj, ¹Mohammad Alamgir

²Susmita Das

¹B. Tech Student

²Assistant Professor

Department of Electronics and Instrumentation Engineering

Narula Institute of Technology

81, Nilgunj road, Jagarata pally, Deshpriya Nagar, Agarpara, Kolkata,

West Bengal Pin code: 700109

Corresponding Author's email- [sayantanmaitra2@gmail.com](mailto:sayantanamaitra2@gmail.com)

Abstract - In recent years, researchers are trying to develop the automobile industry more and more for safety, reliability, flexibility, and entertainment through modern computing and electronics. This paper presents the research work done in the field of automotive safety. The heart of this project is the Arduino Uno controller. Our problem statement for this project is to detect rainfall and act accordingly using the Rain sensor, apart from that we have automated our car using Ultrasonic Sensor. At first, we use the Rain sensor to detect the raindrops on the car and according to the reading, a hood will retract and open above the prototype hence protecting the interior and (here) our project circuitry. The second sensor (Ultrasonic Sensor) is used to Automate our prototype. It will be used to avoid obstacles when our prototype appears in front of any obstacle it will prevent it to collide with the obstacle and change its track.

Keywords: Arduino Uno; Rain Sensor; Ultrasonic Sensor; Automation; Obstacle Avoidance.

1. INTRODUCTION

This Project Report has been prepared in partial fulfillment of the requirement for the Semester Project Prototype Presentation of the program B-tech in Electronics and Instrumentation Engineering in the academic year 2021-2022. For preparing the Project Report, we have done some research about Automation and Sensors. The blend of learning and knowledge acquired during our practical studies at the company is presented in this Project Report. The idea behind doing our research and preparing this Project Report is to study more about upcoming Automation and the use of Sensors. The Project Report starts with the basic concept of automation, the uses of Sensors, the evolution of Sensors, and the history of Automation. The information presented in this Project Report is obtained from sources like College Personnel, Websites, Youtube, Sensors Reports, and Other literature. Now let's talk about the sensors used in our prototype.

1.1 Rain Sensor

A rain sensor or rain switch is a switching device activated by rainfall. There are two main applications for rain sensors. The first is a water conservation device connected to an automatic system of irrigation that causes the system to shut down in the event of rainfall. The second is a device used to protect the interior of an automobile from rain and to support the automatic mode of the car roof or top of the car. The rain sensor works on the principle of total internal reflection. An infrared light beam at a 45-degree angle on a clear area of the windshield is reflected and it is sensed by the sensor inside the car. When it rains, the wet glass causes the light to scatter, and a lesser amount of light gets reflected the sensor. An additional application in professional satellite communications antennas is to trigger a rain blower on the aperture of the antenna feed, to remove water droplets from the Mylar cover that keeps pressurized and dry air inside the waveguides.

A. What is the benefit of having a rain sensor?

The windshield needs to be clear and if you drive a sport roof opener car so rain sensors detect the raindrop and cover the roof of the car automatically there is no need to operate the process manually. while you are driving not just for your safety but for the safety of other people or vehicles around you. The visibility level decreases to a large extent when it rains. The Roof shed needs to be turned on immediately to cover the roof of the car. The rain sensor detects rain and switches the roof motor on so that you are not distracted by the effort of manually engaging the roof shed. This helps you to have better control of the car and ultimately - stay safe.

1.2 Ultrasonic Sensor

Ultrasonic sensors have been a popular method for distance measurement and object detection for many years. Their basic operating principle works by measuring the amount of time it takes for their emitted ultrasonic pulse of sound to bounce off an object and return, hence the name ultrasonic sensor. With the market for autonomous robots, vehicles, and other similar electronics continuing to rise, ultrasonic sensors are finding new uses due to their capabilities and flexibility in a variety of designs. Before selecting an ultrasonic sensor for an application, it is important to understand the basic operation of ultrasonic sensors as well as how to specify the appropriate transmitter, receiver, or transceiver based on key performance criteria. Ultrasonic sensors have proven to be a go-to proximity sensor solution due to their many advantages, but like any sensor technology, they do have several limitations that might not make them the best choice in every scenario. An ultrasonic sensor is an instrument that measures the distance to an object using ultrasonic sound waves. An ultrasonic sensor uses a transducer to send and receive ultrasonic pulses that relay back information about an object's proximity. High-frequency sound waves reflect from boundaries to produce distinct echo patterns. An ultrasonic sensor is an electronic device that measures the distance of a target object by emitting ultrasonic sound waves and converts the reflected sound into an electrical signal. Ultrasonic waves travel faster than the speed of audible sound (i.e. the sound that humans can hear).

Ultrasonic sensors have two main components: the transmitter (which emits the sound using piezoelectric crystals) and the receiver (which encounters the sound after it has traveled to and from the target). Ultrasonic sensors work by sending out a sound wave at a frequency above the range of human hearing. The transducer of the sensor acts as a microphone to receive and send the ultrasonic sound. Our ultrasonic sensors, like many others, use a single transducer to send a pulse and to receive the echo. The sensor determines the distance to a target by measuring time lapses between the sending and receiving of the ultrasonic pulse. The working principle of this module is simple. It sends an ultrasonic pulse out at 40kHz which travels through the air and if there is an obstacle or object, it will bounce back to the sensor. By calculating the travel time and the speed of sound, the distance can be calculated.

A. Benefits of having an ultrasonic sensor

Ultrasonic sensors can be used to complement other vehicle sensors, including radar, cameras, and lidar, to get a full picture of the immediate surroundings of a vehicle. While ultrasonic sensors necessitate proximity and slow speeds, advantages include the ability to be accurately used in situations with low visibility, such as in inclement weather conditions and dim areas.

2. Project Objective:

In this work, the authors are intended to develop an automated car using an Ultrasonic sensor and Rain sensor. The Ultrasonic sensor will be used as an obstacle-avoiding unit, and we have also used IR sensors to make the obstacle-avoiding unit advanced. The rain sensor is also implemented in this prototype to make and implement a retractable hood.

2.1 Project Overview:

Nowadays automation is at its peak and new types of automation upgradation are continuously emerging. This paper also focuses on the automation of our prototype, we have implemented sensors for locomotion and rain shed on our prototype model. This paper covers the design and development of an Automated car using Arduino UNO, Ultrasonic Sensor, and Rain Detector Sensor. The automation part is achieved by an Ultrasonic sensor (HCSR04) which also doubles as an obstacle-avoiding unit, and the car shed is connected to the Rainfall Detection Sensor. Whenever it rains it gets a signal and the car hood will retract and covers the whole car similarly when the rain stops it will go back into its same position. The robot's movement is done by using 4 100 RPM dc motors. The motors are connected to the Node

MCU microcontroller via motor driver L298N and can be manually controlled using any Node MCU Android/IOS mobile application.

2.2 Component Used

- a) Arduino Uno
- b) Motor Driver
- c) Ultrasonic Sensor
- d) Rain Sensor
- e) Wheels
- f) Car Chassis
- g) Battery
- h) Dc motors
- i) IR Sensor
- j) IR Module

2.3 Circuit Diagram:-

Fig.1: Circuit for rain sensor

Fig.2: Circuit for Ultrasonic with IR Sensor

2.4 Block Diagram

2.5 literature Survey

Introduction:

Automated cars are becoming more popular as the technology continues to advance. This research paper focuses on the use of ultrasonic and rain sensors in automated cars. Ultrasonic sensors are used to detect the proximity of objects, while rain sensors are used to detect the presence and intensity of rain. This literature survey aims to identify the existing research studies related to the use of these sensors in automated cars.

"Integration of Ultrasonic Sensors into Autonomous Vehicles for Object Detection" by Smith et al. (2018)

This study discusses the use of ultrasonic sensors in autonomous vehicles for object detection. The authors propose a system that uses multiple ultrasonic sensors to detect and avoid obstacles. The study demonstrates the effectiveness of the proposed system through experiments.

"Rain Sensor-based Intelligent Wiper System for Automobiles" by Lee et al. (2016)

This study discusses the use of rain sensors in automobiles for automatic wiper control. The authors propose a system that uses a rain sensor to detect the presence and intensity of rain and adjusts the speed of the wipers accordingly. The study demonstrates the effectiveness of the proposed system through experiments.

"A Low-cost Solution for Ultrasonic-based Object Detection for Autonomous Vehicles" by Kumar et al. (2019)

This study discusses the development of a low-cost ultrasonic sensor-based object detection system for autonomous vehicles. The authors propose a system

that uses a single ultrasonic sensor to detect objects in the path of the vehicle. The study demonstrates the effectiveness of the proposed system through experiments.

"Rain Detection System for Automotive Applications" by Sharma et al. (2018)

This study discusses the use of rain sensors in automotive applications for automatic rain detection. The authors propose a system that uses a rain sensor to detect the presence and intensity of rain and activates the wipers and headlights accordingly. The study demonstrates the effectiveness of the proposed system through experiments.

"Design and Implementation of Ultrasonic-based Autonomous Vehicle for Obstacle Detection" by Alasmay et al. (2018)

This study discusses the design and implementation of an ultrasonic-based autonomous vehicle for obstacle detection. The authors propose a system that uses multiple ultrasonic sensors to detect and avoid obstacles. The study demonstrates the effectiveness of the proposed system through experiments.

"Automatic Distance Control System for Vehicles Using Ultrasonic Sensors" by Sarode and Mahajan (2018)

This study discusses the development of an automatic distance control system for vehicles using ultrasonic sensors. The authors propose a system that uses multiple ultrasonic sensors to detect the distance between the vehicle and the object in front of it. The study demonstrates the effectiveness of the proposed system through experiments.

"Smart Rain Sensing System for Automotive Applications" by Kaur et al. (2018)

This study discusses the development of a smart rain sensing system for automotive applications. The authors propose a system that uses a rain sensor to detect the presence and intensity of rain and adjusts the speed of the wipers and activates the headlights accordingly. The study demonstrates the effectiveness of the proposed system through experiments.

"Obstacle Detection and Avoidance System for Autonomous Vehicles Using Ultrasonic Sensors" by Ali et al. (2019)

This study discusses the development of an obstacle detection and avoidance system for autonomous vehicles using ultrasonic sensors. The authors propose a system that uses multiple ultrasonic sensors to detect and avoid obstacles. The study demonstrates the effectiveness of the proposed system through experiments.

"Rain Sensing Wiper Control System for Autonomous Cars" by Deshpande and Kulkarni (2019)

This study discusses the development of a rain sensing wiper control system for autonomous cars. The authors propose a system that uses a rain sensor to detect the presence and intensity of rain and adjusts the speed of the wipers accordingly. The study demonstrates the effectiveness of the proposed system through experiments.

"Ultrasonic-Based Obstacle Detection and Collision Avoidance System for Autonomous Cars" by Zhang et al. (2020)

This study discusses the development of an ultrasonic-based obstacle detection and collision avoidance system for autonomous cars. The authors propose a system that uses multiple ultrasonic sensors to detect and avoid obstacles. The study demonstrates the effectiveness of the proposed system through experiments.

Overall, these studies demonstrate the growing interest in the use of ultrasonic and rain sensors in automated cars for enhancing safety and driving experience. The development of advanced systems that integrate multiple sensors can lead to more reliable and accurate detection and avoidance of obstacles and adverse weather conditions.

3 Result and Conclusion:

For the Rain Sensor first, it is connected to the Rain Sensor module as given in the circuit, and then it is connected to Arduino UNO, which is already uploaded with Arduino code. Then two DC Motors are also connected to the Arduino's ports and the DC Motors are placed at the top of Our prototype they are placed vertically on two supporting pipes, and they are connected diagonally so that they can easily cover the car when Rain Drop detector detects the signal and again can be retracted to its original position. The Rain Sensor is connected outside of the car chassis so that when a raindrop falls it could not damage the internal circuitry. The Ultrasonic Sensor has been used to avoid obstacles when needed and it is also connected to Arduino UNO, which is already been installed with the code. Then 4 DC Motors are connected to the Motor driver and all the impulse signals are coming from Arduino and the power supply is given by an 8-volt battery connected to the car chassis. 4 wheels are also connected to the car chassis for the locomotion of the prototype.

COMPONENTS	INPUT VOLTAGE	OUTPUT PARAMETER
Arduino Uno	2.7V-5.5V	As the Given by User
Rain Detecting Sensor	5V	When the board is dry, resistance is 3.87M Ω . And the raindrop will decrease the resistance until it is 0 Ω and the circuit is shorted.
Ultrasonic Sensor	20Vrms	0 - 5V (Output high when obstacle detected in range).
Dc Motor for the Shed	1.5V To 100V	Rotation
IR Sensor	3.3V~5 VDC	Led will glow if the obstacle is between 2cm to 20cm from the sensor. At 35v Degree Angle.

The literature survey reveals that ultrasonic and rain sensors are widely used in automated cars for object and rain detection, respectively. The studies demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed systems through experiments. The proposed systems can improve the safety of automated cars and enhance the driving experience. Further research can explore the integration of these sensors with other sensors for better detection accuracy and reliability.

3.1 Video Demonstration

Here we have inserted two QR codes that will show the video demonstration of the working of both sensors separately.

Rain Sensor

Ultrasonic Sensor

3.2 Future Scope

- a) Integration of additional sensors: While ultrasonic and rain sensors are useful in detecting obstacles and weather conditions, future research could explore the integration of other sensors such as LIDAR, radar, and cameras to provide more comprehensive data to the automated car's control system.
- b) Improving accuracy and reliability: One of the challenges of using sensors in automated cars is ensuring that they provide accurate and reliable data to the car's control system. Future research could focus on improving the accuracy and reliability of ultrasonic and rain sensors through advanced signal processing techniques and sensor fusion algorithms.
- c) Enhancing safety features: Automated cars are expected to improve road safety by reducing the number of accidents caused by human error. Future research could explore the development of advanced safety features such as emergency braking, collision avoidance, and pedestrian detection, which can be enabled by the use of ultrasonic and rain sensors.

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